

1 **A molecular barcode for kinase and phosphatase-based therapeutic intervention in metastasis to**
2 **the liver in patients with metastatic breast cancer.**

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7 Stage IV breast cancer has metastasized to the brain, lungs, liver, and/or the skeletal system and is
8 exceedingly difficult to treat (1). Challenges include lack of available therapeutic targets, resistance to
9 standard chemotherapies, weak antitumor immune responses resulting from a limited necrotic response
10 which activates immunity and (2-4), given a novel compound, toxicity resulting from off-target and tissue
11 non-specific activity. We present here a molecular barcode (5, 6) which represents a conserved (across
12 liver metastasis cohorts) set of differentially expressed kinases, phosphatases and transferases - clinically
13 actionable therapeutic targets. The small molecules that inhibit these enzymes will serve as adjunctives in
14 the treatment of stage IV breast cancer alongside standard chemotherapy and immunotherapy in a novel
15 treatment regiment. In these notes, we describe the kinases and phosphatases that are most highly
16 up-regulated in the liver metastases of patients with metastatic breast cancer. The transferases activated
17 in liver metastasis in humans with metastatic breast cancer are sufficient to retrieve a liver cancer gene
18 signature; we identified HIF3A as a central mediator of the liver metastatic gene expression program.
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Results

We measured total transcription changes in metastasis to the liver (all genes expressed in the primary tumors and liver metastases, and how much the expression of these genes changed when comparing primary tumor to liver metastasis) using microarray data from two independently published breast cancer cohorts (5, 6). We identified one phosphatase, four kinases or kinase-associated molecules, and nine transferases that were differentially expressed to an extent greater than 90% of the tumor transcriptome, whose expression was up-regulated, and whose differential expression and up-regulation was conserved among two independent patient cohorts. Importantly, our findings are exact (microarray-based), with differential expression status obtained using only human tissues and validated across cohorts. Therapeutic index, which in large part defines the toxicity and safety profile of the inhibitor, is intrinsically linked to differential expression of the target (7).

Phosphatases

G6PC

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
206952_at	1.27E-05	-5.041347	3.18591	-2.8709147	G6PC	102/22283	

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
100146610_TGI_at	3.20E-05	-4.61	2.288685	-2.88	G6PC	312/52378	

Kinases

GCKR

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
206867_at	3.82E-04	-3.911857	0.00653	-0.9731868	GCKR	187/	

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
100158439_TGI_at	1.52E-04	-4.13	0.850275	-2.13	GCKR	541/	

KHK

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
100135476_TGI_at	1.23E-03	-3.44	-1.063198	-1.37	KHK	1206/	

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
211028_s_at	2.40E-03	-3.262107	-1.685	-1.5824959	KHK	269/	

PCK1

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
208383_s_at	5.39E-06	-5.319951	3.9938	-4.0655372	PCK1	87/	

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
100138418_TGI_at	1.09E-02	-2.65	-3.018178	-5.65E-01	PCK1	3505/	

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PFKFB1

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
207537_at	5.04E-02	-2.023185	-4.38066	-0.7497381	PFKFB1	1357/	

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	Gene	Rank	%DE
100144051_TGI_at	1.22E-02	-2.61	-3.110842	-1.02	PFKFB1	3719/	

Transferases

GAMT

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205354_at	4.79E-03	-3.003328	-2.31453	-1.3253762	GAMT	351/	

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
100129433_TGI_at	2.18E-04	-4.01	0.519581	-1.56	GAMT	613/	

GATM

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
203178_at	5.39E-04	-3.793561	-0.31143	-1.935212	GATM	199/	

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
100143553_TGI_at	1.76E-03	-3.32	-1.388053	-1.79	GATM	1403/	

GLYAT

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
222083_at	3.06E-03	-3.171942	-1.90763	-1.551224	GLYAT	291/	

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
100131799_TGI_at	3.46E-03	-3.08	-1.997719	-1.7	GLYAT	1911/	

MAT1A

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205813_s_at	5.66E-06	-5.304454	3.94875	-2.9200997	MAT1A	88/	

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
100158012_TGI_at	3.65E-06	-5.26	4.306093	-3.41	MAT1A	158/	

NAA60

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
45526_g_at	8.74E-02	-1.756612	-4.83514	-0.258248	NAA60	2107/	

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
100124903_TGI_at	1.22E-02	-2.61	-3.113345	-4.09E-01	NAA60	3726/	

OTC

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
207200_at	9.34E-02	-1.722628	-4.88925	-0.9531176	OTC	2225/	

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
100146160_TGI_at	1.69E-04	-4.09	0.752567	-2.47	OTC	559/	

SULT2A1

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
206293_at	3.07E-04	-3.987516	0.21185	-2.0274323	SULT2A1	181/	

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
100151581_TGI_at	6.79E-06	-5.07	3.728868	-3.65	SULT2A1	194/	

TAT

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
206916_x_at	1.17E-03	-3.520898	-1.02834	-1.4844908	TAT	229/	

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
100145058_TGI_at	8.71E-05	-4.3	1.363855	-2.92	TAT	429/	

UGT2B4

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
206505_at	5.92E-06	-5.289774	3.90608	-3.8759937	UGT2B4	89/	

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
100148129_TGI_at	4.15E-06	-5.22	4.185845	-4.12	UGT2B4	170/	

We studied transcriptional co-regulation at the systems level across multiple tissue settings, to discover co-regulated partners/interactors of the nine transferases identified in metastasis to the liver in transformed settings: MAT1A, SULT2A1, OTC, GLYAT, NAA60, GATM, GAMT, TAT and UGT2B4. We identified HIF3A, HNF4A and CCL16 as top co-regulated gene products of transferases activated at the systems level in metastasis to the liver using the transformed breast as a model setting (Figure 1). Gene signature analysis (MSigDB) retrieved two separate liver cancer gene signatures using transferases up-regulated in liver metastasis as query (Figure 2). See also Figure 3 and Figure 4, where the same effectors, HIF3A and HNF4A, were identified using the kinase(s) and phosphatases we identified by blind transcriptome study as query (Figure 3). The kinase(s) and phosphatases we discovered were also sufficient to retrieve liver cancer gene signature using systems biological methods in breast cancer tissue settings (Figure 4).

Figure 1: Transferases activated in liver metastasis are co-regulated with HIF3A.

Figure 2: Transferases activated in liver metastasis in human breast cancer are associated with a liver cancer gene signature.

Term	p-value	q-value	T	A	T&A
SHEN SMARCA2 TARGETS DN	8E-9	4.44E-8	332	93	16
CHIANG LIVER CANCER SUBCLASS PROLIFERATION DN	1.1E-5	1.31E-4	154	93	9
YAMASHITA LIVER CANCER STEM CELL DN	1.2E-3	2.99E-2	74	93	5
WOO LIVER CANCER RECURRENCE DN	1.42E-3	3.26E-2	80	93	5
XU GH1 EXOGENOUS TARGETS UP	1.42E-3	4.7E-2	48	93	4
XU HGF TARGETS REPRESSED BY AKT1 DN	9.51E-3	2.3E-1	76	93	4

Figure 3: Kinases and phosphatases activated in liver metastasis are co-regulated with HIF3A.

Figure 4: Kinases and phosphatases activated in liver metastasis retrieve liver cancer gene signatures.

Term	p-value	q-value	T	A	T&A
YAMASHITA LIVER CANCER STEM CELL DN	8.9E-6	1.55E-4	74	91	7
SHEN SMARCA2 TARGETS DN	2.8E-5	1.55E-4	332	91	12
CHIANG LIVER CANCER SUBCLASS PROLIFERATION DN	8.66E-4	1.04E-2	154	91	7
MOREAUX MULTIPLE MYELOMA BY TACI UP	1.24E-2	6.22E-2	367	91	9
URS ADIPOCYTE DIFFERENTIATION UP	1.24E-2	1.03E-1	60	91	4
CAIRO HEPATOBLASTOMA DN	2.15E-2	1.5E-1	264	91	7
XU HGF TARGETS REPRESSED BY AKT1 DN	2.15E-2	1.82E-1	76	91	4
WOO LIVER CANCER RECURRENCE DN	2.15E-2	1.93E-1	80	91	4

Discussion

Tumor cells thrive using growth factor and growth factor-like signals that are transduced to the nucleus to sustain proliferative activity (8-10). Metastatic cells survive in the nascent niche during colonization by up-regulating specific gene products (including kinases and phosphatases) to sustain survival signals in a tissue environment that differs from which it was derived (in breast cancer, the breast) (11). These kinases and phosphatases (12, 13) become differentially expressed based on their up-regulation; we measured and captured their activity here. We hypothesize specific blockade of kinase and phosphatase targets in liver metastases will, resulting from lack of ability to transduced growth/survival signals, result in necrotic and apoptotic activity (2-4), particularly when combined with standard chemotherapies. Immunotherapy approaches produce optimal responses given tumor antigen/neoantigen from necrotic and/or apoptotic tumor cells. Combining inhibitors from this molecular barcode with standard chemotherapy and novel immunotherapy approaches can provide invigorated anti-tumor immune responses in the presence of optimized tumor killing. In a separate manuscript, we described re-activation of MHC-I (15).

References

1. Thomas, A., Khan, S.A., Chrischilles, E.A. and Schroeder, M.C., 2016. Initial surgery and survival in stage IV breast cancer in the United States, 1988-2011. *JAMA surgery*, 151(5), pp.424-431.
2. Bartholomae, W.C., Rininsland, F.H., Eisenberg, J.C., Boehm, B.O., Lehmann, P.V. and Tary-Lehmann, M., 2004. T cell immunity induced by live, necrotic, and apoptotic tumor cells. *The Journal of Immunology*, 173(2), pp.1012-1022.
3. Tesniere, A., Panaretakis, T., Kepp, O., Apetoh, L., Ghiringhelli, F., Zitvogel, L. and Kroemer, G., 2008. Molecular characteristics of immunogenic cancer cell death. *Cell Death & Differentiation*, 15(1), pp.3-12.
4. Galluzzi, L., Buqué, A., Kepp, O., Zitvogel, L. and Kroemer, G., 2017. Immunogenic cell death in cancer and infectious disease. *Nature Reviews Immunology*, 17(2), pp.97-111.
5. Sinn, B.V., Fu, C., Lau, R., Litton, J., Tsai, T.H., Murthy, R., Tam, A., Andreopoulou, E., Gong, Y., Murthy, R. and Gould, R., 2019. SETER/PR: a robust 18-gene predictor for sensitivity to endocrine therapy for metastatic breast cancer. *NPJ breast cancer*, 5(1), p.16.
6. Tobin, N.P., Lundberg, A., Lindström, L.S., Harrell, J.C., Foukakis, T., Carlsson, L., Einbeigi, Z., Linderholm, B.K., Loman, N., Malmberg, M. and Fernö, M., 2017. PAM50 provides prognostic information when applied to the lymph node metastases of advanced breast cancer patients. *Clinical Cancer Research*, 23(23), pp.7225-7231.
7. Muller, P.Y. and Milton, M.N., 2012. The determination and interpretation of the therapeutic index in drug development. *Nature reviews Drug discovery*, 11(10), pp.751-761.
8. Sporn, M.B. and Roberts, A.B., 1985. Autocrine growth factors and cancer. *Nature*, 313(6005), pp.745-747.
9. Shamji, A.F., Nghiem, P. and Schreiber, S.L., 2003. Integration of growth factor and nutrient signaling: implications for cancer biology. *Molecular cell*, 12(2), pp.271-280.
10. Wilson, T.R., Fridlyand, J., Yan, Y., Penuel, E., Burton, L., Chan, E., Peng, J., Lin, E., Wang, Y., Sosman, J. and Ribas, A., 2012. Widespread potential for growth-factor-driven resistance to anticancer kinase inhibitors. *Nature*, 487(7408), pp.505-509.

1 11. Satcher, R.L. and Zhang, X.H.F., 2022. Evolving cancer–niche interactions and therapeutic targets
2 during bone metastasis. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 22(2), pp.85-101.

3 12. Östman, A., Hellberg, C. and Böhmer, F.D., 2006. Protein-tyrosine phosphatases and cancer.
4 *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 6(4), pp.307-320.

5 13. Blume-Jensen, P. and Hunter, T., 2001. Oncogenic kinase signalling. *Nature*, 411(6835),
6 pp.355-365.

7 14. Zhu, Q., Wong, A.K., Krishnan, A., Aure, M.R., Tadych, A., Zhang, R., Corney, D.C., Greene, C.S.,
8 Bongo, L.A., Kristensen, V.N. and Charikar, M., 2015. Targeted exploration and analysis of large
9 cross-platform human transcriptomic compendia. *Nature methods*, 12(3), pp.211-214.

10 15. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. UBE2L6 controls expression of MHC class I genes, and tumors activate
11 UBE2L6 to silence MHC-I.

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Methods

We utilized two separate primary human breast and metastatic liver metastasis cohorts, using only human tissues to identify a) conserved, b) differentially expressed and c) up-regulated d) kinases, phosphatases and transferases in humans with liver metastasis resulting from metastatic breast cancer. We used R-based computational software to extract quantitative information regarding differential expression (GEO2R). In the first liver metastasis cohort (GSE124647), the whole transcriptome of $n=19$ primary breast tumors was compared to that of $n=16$ liver metastases. In the second cohort (GSE56493), the whole transcriptome of $n=19$ primary breast tumors was compared to that of $n=27$ liver metastases. We used SEEK (14) for transcriptional co-regulation analysis.